

Implementing Memento RFC 7089 for Invenio Digital Library Software

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Project Specification

Implement support of Memento (RFC 7089 [1]), an HTTP framework permitting users to ‘browse the web in the past’ via a browser extension, for Invenio digital library software. Implement an HTTP API that exposes historical versions of the research objects managed by Invenio.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	4
2	Memento protocol	4
2.1	Patterns	4
2.2	Specification	4
3	Memento at Invenio	6
3.1	Modules	6
3.2	Endpoints	7
3.3	Exposing past record revisions	7
4	Conclusion	8

1 Introduction

Memento is a protocol that adds time dimension to Web, allowing to browse and discover the historical versions of Web resources. The development of the protocol was supported by the Library of Congress. Now it is published as RFC 7089 proposal to the HTTP standard. Currently it is used for time navigation at Internet Archive, for browsing the historical versions of records at DBpedia Archive, Stanford Libraries Web Archive, and other digital collections [2].

Invenio digital library software would benefit from the implementation of the Memento protocol, because it will enable the users and automatic Invenio API consumers, like Web crawlers, to easily access the historical versions of library records.

2 Memento protocol

2.1 Patterns

The Memento protocol is defined in several patterns that differ in roles of the API endpoints and HTTP response codes. The pattern ‘2.1’ [3] requires that the original resource and its historical snapshot have different base URIs. This approach is consistent with Invenio’s modular architecture which is based on Flask blueprints that rely on URIs for separation of concerns. For the reason of being more suitable for integrating into Invenio, the pattern 2.1 is assumed throughout the paper.

2.2 Specification

This section will provide a brief overview of HTTP interactions between user agent and Memento-enabled server as per the Memento protocol.

Let R be the original library record (*resource*), G_R the TimeGate endpoint for datetime negotiation, T_R the TimeMap endpoint for discovering the historical versions of R , and $M_R(D)$ the *Memento*, a historical version of R corresponding to the datetime D . Denote UA the HTTP user agent.

TimeGate G_R discovery for given resource R . The response to every HEAD/GET request to the URI of the resource R includes a Link header that contains the URI of the G_R TimeGate endpoint.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{UA} & \xrightarrow{\text{HTTP HEAD/GET}} \text{URI}(R) \\ \text{UA} & \xleftarrow[\text{Link: URI}(G_R)]{\text{HTTP 200}} \text{URI}(R) \end{aligned}$$

The *Link* header should conform to the RFC 5988 [4] link header format:

```
|| <URI-G_R>
   ; rel="timegate"
```

TimeMap T_R discovery. Datetime negotiation for given TimeGate G_R . The response to a HEAD/GET request to the URI of the TimeGate G_R includes links to all of the other Memento protocol endpoints, which allows the client to learn the URI of the TimeMap endpoint T_R . If the request has the desired date D specified with *Accept-Datetime* header, the response includes a link to the most appropriate historical version of the resource $M_R(D')$.

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{UA} \xrightarrow{\text{HTTP HEAD/GET; Accept-Datetime: } D} \text{URI}(G_R) \\
 \text{UA} \xleftarrow[\text{Vary; Link: URI}(R), \text{URI}(T_R)]{\text{HTTP 302; Location: URI}(M_R(D'))} \text{URI}(G_R)
 \end{array}$$

The *Link* header, similarly, should conform to the RFC 5988 link format.

```

<URI-R>
  ; rel="original",
<URI-G_R>
  ; rel="timegate",
<URI-T_R>
  ; rel="timemap";
  ; type="application/link-format"
<URI-M_R(D)>
  ; rel="memento"
  ; datetime="D"

```

The date D in the *Accept-Datetime* and all other dates should be in the standard HTTP-date form [6].

The *Vary* header is used to convey that the datetime negotiation is possible. For Memento pattern 2.1 it is always provided and includes the `accept-datetime` value.

Accessing Memento $M_R(D)$. The Memento endpoint $M_R(D)$ responds with the historical snapshot of the resource R , and includes links to all of the other Memento protocol endpoints.

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{UA} \xrightarrow{\text{HTTP GET; Accept-Datetime: } D} \text{URI}(M_R(D)) \\
 \text{UA} \xleftarrow[\text{Link: URI}(R), \text{URI}(T_R), \text{URI}(G_R)]{\text{HTTP 200; Memento-Datetime: } D'} \text{URI}(M_R(D))
 \end{array}$$

The *Link* header is similar to that of the *TimeGate* response.

```

<URI-R>
  ; rel="original",
<URI-G_R>
  ; rel="timegate",
<URI-T_R>
  ; rel="timemap";
  ; type="application/link-format"
<URI-M_R(D[prev])>
  ; rel="memento prev"
  ; datetime="D[prev]"
<URI-M_R(D[next])>
  ; rel="memento next"
  ; datetime="D[next]"
<URI-M_R(D[last])>
  ; rel="memento last"
  ; datetime="D[last]"

```

Discovery of the historical versions for given $T(R)$. The response to a HEAD/GET request to the TimeGate endpoint T_R includes links to all of the other Memento protocol endpoints, and a list of all the available Mementos in the response body.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{UA} &\xrightarrow{\text{HTTP HEAD/GET}} \text{URI}(T_R) \\ \text{UA} &\xleftarrow{\text{HTTP 200}} \text{URI}(T_R) \end{aligned}$$

The response should conform to the RFC 6690 [5] link format, which is similar to the format of the *Links* header described previously, only provided in the response body.

```
<URI-R>
  ; rel="original",
<URI-T_R>
  ; rel="self"
  ; type="application/link-format"
  ; from="D[start]"
  ; until="D[end]",
<URI-G_R>
  ; rel="timegate",
<URI-M_R(D[start])>
  ; rel="first memento"
  ; datetime="D[start]"
<URI-M_R(D[end])>
  ; rel="last memento"
  ; datetime="D[end]"
<URI-M_R(D[i])>
  ; rel="memento"
  ; datetime="D[i]"
```

It is also possible via the specification for the TimeGate responses to be paginated. See the RFC 7089 for details.

3 Memento at Invenio

3.1 Modules

The implementation of the Memento protocol for Invenio consists of work on two modules.

In order to facilitate the browsing and discovering of the historical records for Invenio, the API for accessing older revisions of library records has to be available. Such functionality belongs to the *record* Invenio module.

The Memento-specific entities of *TimeGate* and *TimeMap* API endpoints belong in the separate *memento* module.

3.2 Endpoints

Based on the chosen module architecture, the URIs for the Memento protocol were chosen as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\text{URI}(R) &= \text{record}/\text{ID}(R)/ \\ \text{URI}(M_R(D)) &= \text{record}/\text{ID}(R)/?\text{wayback} = \text{REV}(D') \\ \text{URI}(G_R) &= \text{timegate}/\text{record}/\text{ID}(R) \\ \text{URI}(T_R) &= \text{timemap}/\text{record}/\text{ID}(R)\end{aligned}$$

Where $\text{REV}(D)$ denotes the record revision number which corresponds to the datetime D .

3.3 Exposing past record revisions

Invenio library records are stored in a base format (MARC or JSON), while other representations (HTML) are derived from the base ones using templates. The base format is versioned by default.

In order to expose the historical versions of the record, one approach would be to render it using the appropriate version of the record data in a base format by applying the current template. The problem with this technique is that with the current template the render may not look the same as it did at the requested time in the past both in the sense of visual appearance and content. Not all fields could be rendered, or conversely, some fields that were absent in the historical version of the record data, could appear in the current template. To mitigate, one could also version the templates, but even so, the templates can depend on some environment variables that might not be there anymore or have invalid values at the rendering time.

Another approach would be to snapshot and save the final renders, not the base format. Such approach will make the Memento to be as close to the original historical version of the record as it is possible. This would, however, come at the cost of processing power and potentially massive additional storage.

The code addressing the exposing of the past revision metadata using the first approach of rendering the past record data using the current template has been submitted on the Invenio Github [7].

4 Conclusion

The users of the digital libraries powered by Invenio would benefit from the implementation of the Memento protocol, as it will provide an easy way to access the past versions of the library records as of now. This project has investigated the protocol details, discovered the potential problems, outlined the design of the protocol implementation, and implemented part of the protocol. Further work needs to be done to make the implementation of the Memento protocol in the Invenio fully complete and ready to use.

References

- [1] Memento protocol
RFC 7089
<http://www.mementoweb.org/guide/rfc>
- [2] Memento Depot
<http://mementoweb.org/depot/>
- [3] Memento protocol pattern 2.1
RFC 7089
<http://www.mementoweb.org/guide/rfc/#Pattern2.1>
- [4] Web Linking
RFC 5988
<https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc5988>
- [5] Link Format
RFC 6690
<https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc6690>
- [6] HTTP 1.1 Protocol
RFC 2616
<https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc2616>
- [7] 'Records: expose past revisions' issue on Github
<https://github.com/inveniosoftware/invenio/issues/1990>